

RADIO MEAN LABELING, RADIO MEAN SQUARE LABELING, RADIO ANALYTICAL MEAN LABELING, AND RADIO ANALYTICAL MEAN SQUARE LABELING FOR CERTAIN GRAPHS

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Abstract:

Radio Mean Labeling, Radio Mean Square Labeling, Radio Analytical Mean Labeling, Radio Analytical Mean Square Labeling of a connected graph G , is a one-to-one mapping $f:V(G) \rightarrow \{N\}$ for any two vertices x and y of G . The radio mean number of f , $rmn(f)$, is the maximum number assigned to any vertex of G . The radio mean number of G , $rmn(G)$ is the minimum value of $rmn(f)$ taken over all labelings of f of G . In this work, we will determine the radio mean number of graphs with diameter two for certain graphs, such as the Butterfly graph, Friendship graph, Star graph, and Complete Bipartite graph.

MSC: 05C05, 05C07, 05C12, 05C35

Key words: Radio Mean labeling, Radio Square Mean labeling, Radio Analytic Mean labeling, Radio Analytic Mean Square labeling, Butterfly graph, Friendship graph, Star graph, and Complete bipartite graph.

1. Introduction:

Graph theory plays a crucial role in various fields of mathematics, including computer science, as well as in communication, neural networks, robotics, and signal systems. Researchers have developed many labelings, such as Radio Mean, Radio Mean Square, Radio Analytic Mean, Radio Analytic Mean Square, Radio Geometric Mean Labelings. There are specific conditions for graph labelling to make it graceful. The important condition in graceful labeling is that the labeling must be distinct. In 2001, Chartrand introduced the concept of radio labelling, which extends to the ideas of graceful labeling [1].

In this paper, we consider only the finite, simple, and undirected graph $G(V, E)$ where $V(G)$, $E(G)$ are the vertex set and edge set of G , respectively. The order of the graph G is the cardinality of the vertex set, i.e., $|V(G)|$. The number of edges incident on the vertex $v \in V(G)$ is known as the degree of the vertex v , and it is denoted by $d_G(v)$. The first theorem of graph theory, the Handshaking lemma, is used to determine the cardinality of an edge set, i.e., $|E(G)|$ which is also known as the size of G . A path is the alternating sequence of vertices and edges, starting and ending with the vertex, and neither the vertex nor the edge will be repeated

more than once. The number of edges in the path is known as the length of the path. The distance between any two vertices $u, v \in V(G)$, denoted by $d_G(u, v)$ is the length of the shortest path between them. The maximum distances between $v \in V(G)$ and the other vertex of G is known as the eccentricity of v , denoted by $e_G(v)$. For undefined terms, refer to [2].

The Labeling is assigning the positive integers to either the vertices or edges, or both. In [1], we can observe that the Radio Analytical mean Graceful Labeling for Friendship graph, Star graph, and complete bipartite graph.

In this paper, I computed the graceful labeling for certain graphs with diameter two like butterfly graph, friendship graph, star graph, and complete bipartite graph.

Preliminaries:

1. **Butterfly Graph:** The graph obtained by inserting vertices into every wing, assuming that the sum of the inserted vertices in every wing is the same.
2. **Friendship Graph:** The friendship graph is obtained by joining the copies of C_3 with a common vertex known as the central vertex.
3. **Star Graph:** A star graph is a tree in which the central vertex is connected to all other vertices.
4. **Complete Bipartite Graph:** It is a type of bipartite graph where every vertex in one set is connected to every vertex in another set.
5. **Radio Labeling:** Radio labeling of a connected graph G is a one-to-one mapping $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{N\}$ such that for any two distinct vertices x and y of G ,

$$d(x, y) + |f(x) - f(y)| \geq 1 + \text{diam}(G).$$

5.1. RADIO MEAN LABELING

$$d(u, v) + \left| \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} \right| \geq 1 + \text{diam}(G)$$

5.2. RADIO MEAN SQUARE LABELING

$$d(u, v) + \left| \frac{f(u)^2 + f(v)^2}{2} \right| \geq 1 + \text{diam}(G)$$

5.3. RADIO ANALYTIC MEAN LABELING

$$d(u, v) + \left| \frac{|f(u) - f(v)|}{2} \right| \geq 1 + \text{diam}(G)$$

5.4. RADIO ANALYTIC SQUARE LABELING

$$d(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{|f(u)^2 - f(v)^2|}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \text{diam}(G)$$

2. Main Results

Theorem 2.1 The Butterfly graph BF_n for $n \geq 2$ admits graceful labeling for radio mean, radio mean square, radio analytical mean, and radio analytical mean square.

Proof: Let G be the butterfly graph BF_n .

The number of vertices $|V(G)| = 2n+1$ where $n \geq 2$ and the number of edges $|E(G)| = 2(2n-1)$.

Let us define the vertex set $V(G)$ as $U \cup V \cup W$ where $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $W = \{w\}$ and the edge set $E(G)$ as $\{(w, u_i) : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{(w, v_i) : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{(u_i, u_{i+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{(v_i, v_{i+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$

Consider w as the central vertex, U be the vertices on the left wing, V be the vertices on the right wing.

Now, define the function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

WLG,

Let $f(u_1) = 1$, $f(u_n) = 2$, $f(v_1) = 3$, $f(v_n) = 4$.

$f(u_{i+1}) = f(v_n) + i$, $f(v_{i+1}) = f(u_{n-1}) + i$, $f(w) = f(v_{n-1}) + 1, \forall 1 \leq i \leq n-1$.

\therefore We can observe that the Butterfly Graph BF_n admits the radio graceful mean labeling, radio graceful mean square labeling, radio graceful analytical mean labeling, and radio analytical mean square labeling.

Fig.1. Butterfly Graph (BF_6)

Theorem 2.2 The Friendship graph F_n^m for $n \geq 7$, $m \geq 3$ admits graceful labeling for radio mean, radio mean square, and radio analytical mean.

Proof: Let G be the friendship graph F_n^m .

The number of vertices $|V(G)| = n$ and the number of edges $|E(G)| = n + m - 1$, where $n \geq 7$ (number of vertices) and $m \geq 3$ (number of triangles).

Now, let us define the vertex set $V(G) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and the edge set is defined as

$$E(G) = \{(v_n, v_i) : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{(v_i, v_{i+1}) : i = 1, 3, \dots, n-2\}.$$

Let us consider v_n as the central vertex.

Now, define the function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

WLG,

Let $f(v_1) = 1$, $f(v_2) = m + 1$, $f(v_{n-2}) = m$, $f(v_{n-1}) = n - 1$ and $f(v_n) = n$.

For odd vertices: $f(v_{i+1}) = f(v_{i-1}) + 1$; $i = 2, 4, \dots, 2m - 1$.

For even vertices: $f(v_{i+2}) = m + \left(\frac{2+i}{2}\right)$; $i = 2, 4, \dots, n - 1$.

\therefore We can observe that the Friendship Graph F_n^m admits the radio graceful mean labeling, radio graceful mean square labeling, and radio graceful analytical mean labeling.

Fig. 2. Friendship Graph (F_{17}^8)

Theorem 2.3 The Star graph S_n for $n \geq 3$ admits graceful labeling for radio mean, radio mean square, and radio analytical mean.

Proof: Let G be the star graph S_n .

The number of vertices $|V(G)| = n$ and the number of edges $|E(G)| = n - 1$, where $n \geq 3$.

Now, let us define the vertex set $V(G) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and the edge set is defined as $E(G) = \{(v_n, v_i) : 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$.

Let us consider v_n as the central vertex.

Now, define the function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ as $f(v_i) = i; 1 \leq i \leq n$.

\therefore We can observe that the Star Graph S_n admits the radio graceful mean labeling, radio graceful mean square labeling, and radio graceful analytical mean labeling.

Fig. 3. Star Graph (S_9)

Theorem 2.4 The Complete Bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ admits graceful labeling for radio mean, radio mean square, and radio analytical mean.

Proof: Let G be the Complete Bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ with the vertices $V = V_1 \cup V_2$ where $V_1 = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m\}$ and $V_2 = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$.

The total number of vertices $|V(G)| = m + n$ and the number of edges $|E(G)| = m * n$.

Let us define the vertex set $V(G)$ as $\{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq m+n\}$ and the edge set $E(G)$ as $\{(v_i, u_j) : 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$.

Now, define the function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ as $f(v_i) = i; 1 \leq i \leq m$ and $f(u_j) = f(v_m) + j; 1 \leq j \leq n$.

\therefore We can observe that the Complete Bipartite Graph $K_{m,n}$ admits the radio graceful mean labeling, radio graceful mean square labeling, and radio graceful analytical mean labeling.

Fig. 4. Complete Bipartite Graph ($K_{4,4}$)

3. Conclusion:

In this paper, we can conclude that any graph with diameter 2 satisfies the radio mean labeling, radio mean square labeling, radio analytical mean labeling, and radio analytical mean square labeling.

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